

Medical Records Search Application Design Outpatient At Rsi Ibnu Sina Padang Year 2023

Alfauzain^{1*}, Mughni Dhastin¹, Ade Wisandra², & Mila Sari³

¹⁻⁴STIKES Dharma Landbouw Padang, Indonesia

*e-mail: alfauzain@gmail.com

Article Information

Received: May 08, 2024

Revised: May 16, 2024

On line: May 17, 2024

Keywords

Search; Information Systems Design;
Electronics

ABSTRACT

The problem at RSI Ibnu Sina Padang in 2023 is that the search for medical records is always done manually with the time needed for 1 medical record $\pm$ 10 minutes, this is because the medical records are not specified or scattered. The purpose of this study is to find out the design of an outpatient medical record search application at RSI Ibnu Sina Padang in 2023. By adopting the type of research, namely Research & Development (R&D) with the prototype development method. The research was conducted from January to July 2023. The number of informants was 5 people, namely 5 runner officers. Conduct data analysis of potentials and problems, collect data, design products, validate designs, improve designs, and test products. The results showed that the process flow for filling in components, especially in the form of searching was done manually which included outpatient registration proof sheets. Application design can be fully implemented. The test results show that the existing components are in accordance with the hospital format and the application of the search process is faster and more efficient than manual search. Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that the design of the outpatient medical record storage information system was in accordance with the hospital format. It is hoped that this research application design can be used in hospitals and this research can be continued by other researchers.

Keywords: Search; Information Systems Design; Electronics

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are required to maintain medical records as stated in (RI Minister of Health Regulation No.24, 2022) Regarding Medical Records, namely: Health facilities are a tool and/or place used to carry out health/fitness management efforts, whether promotive, preventive, curative or rehabilitative, which are carried out with the assistance of the authorities, environmental government and/or network.

Medical record management begins when the patient is received at a medical institution, the activity of recording the patient's medical information while receiving services at the health facility and handling medical record documents which includes organizing the storage and deletion of files from storage to serve requests or borrow for other functions. One of the activities carried out in scientific reports is managing the document storage system. Garage management for recording medical records is very important in a fitness service organization because it can simplify and speed up the retrieval of health documents stored on garage shelves, smooth retrieval from the garage, ease of return, and protect medical documents. documents from risk of robbery, risk of danger. physical, chemical and organic (Ritonga et al., 2019).

According to (Iqromi Nugra, 2020) An internet site is a web which is defined as a collection of pages that display text information, photo statistics, animated information, sound, video and a combination of all of them, both static and dynamic, which form a series of interrelated houses where each is connected. to the community page. (link).

The approach used is Prototype, this improvement mode is useful for developing archive structures. This technique provides the possibility for program development and gadget research to interact with each other through gadget design methods. The prototyping version is also a method that allows developers to create software models, this approach is good to use if consumers cannot provide maximum statistics about the desired requirements. (Yurindra, 2017).

Based on research conducted by (Mirna Septria et al., 2011) entitled "Overview of the Implementation of the Medical Record Document Alignment System in the Filling Room at the Dr. that the coverage or permanent process for the submission of clinical reports which includes storage of scientific file documents which also includes tools for harmonizing medical records with the general work system number P. 01-05 has been created but has not been completely completed. explained, especially regarding officers in the delivery stage prices in particular. so that outpatient registration officers participate in searching for clinical documents on the archive shelves. This causes service to sufferers to take longer.

An initial survey conducted by researchers on February 2 2023 at RSI Ibnu Sina Padang using observation techniques found that medical record search activities were still carried out manually or conventionally, where the process included runner officers receiving prescriptions or proof of patient registration from the registration desk and then , the runner/filling officer will immediately look for the medical record file that matches the medical record number listed on the prescription paper or proof of patient registration.

Based on the results of interviews conducted with one of the runner officers, it was found that searching for 1 medical record file takes $\pm$ 10 minutes, while the results of interviews conducted with the Head of the Medical Records Room at RSI Ibnu Padang explained that the search time for 1 medical record file is 3 minutes and for The distribution activity itself takes 2 minutes with a total time of 5 minutes, then the problem with searching for medical record files is that the location of the files is erratic or scattered, this makes the search process hampered and the location of the storage space is divided into 3 rooms.

RESEARCH METHODS

Type The research applied is in the form of a development method (Research and Development). The research was conducted at RSI Ibnu Sina Padang from January to July 2023, the data source in this research was taken using Purposive Random Sampling, namely a sampling technique with certain considerations, where in this research the data sources were 5 runner officers. The primary data source was obtained through face-to-face interviews with 5 sources, namely 5 runner officers at the hospital with secondary data obtained through existing data at the hospital, including patient medical record numbers, shelf numbers and shelf rows. Data collection techniques use observation and interview techniques as well as data collection tools in the form of recording devices, notebooks, pens and checklist tables.

Data processing in this research was carried out using the stages of the Research and Development method. There are 10 stages in the Research and Development method, but this research was only carried out up to step 6, namely:

a. Potential and Problems

The potential and problems contained in this research are that during the search process problems were still found in the form of searches still being carried out manually and requiring a long time in the search process. To search for medical record files, officers need ± 10 minutes for 1 medical record file. The problem that occurs during the search is that the location of the file is unknown or scattered.

b. Gathering Information

The information collected in this research was obtained through interviewing officers directly. Interviews were conducted in May-June 2023 at RSI Ibnu Sina Padang.

c. Product Design

The product design is adjusted to the officer's needs at the time the interview is conducted. The initial product design includes patient medical record numbers, shelf numbers and shelf rows.

d. Design Validation

Design validation is carried out to assess whether the product design is appropriate or not in accordance with the officer's request. According to the design filling officer, the design for the medical record search process should include the patient's date of birth.

e. Design Improvements

In the process of improving the design, the officers and researchers held discussions and it was found that the design results were in accordance with the officers' requests and the researchers continued the process of making the product.

f. Product Trial

For the product trial, the results were found in the form of an application for searching medical records for borrowing and returning outpatient medical records. Officers assessed that the product was effective and efficient in the processing process. Product trials include logging in to the application, testing patient data input, search data input, loan data input, return data input, and report generation.

RESEARCH RESULT

The next step taken after conducting the survey was application visual modeling, this research used Unified Modeling Language (UML), then the researchers created a database using MySQL and a local server using XAMPP to make it easier for users to carry out the editing, design and application development process.

Website-based Outpatient Medical Record Search Application for the process of searching and returning outpatient medical records for medical record officers at RSI Ibnu Sina Padang is described in use case diagrams, activity diagrams and sequence diagrams.

Figure 1 Use Case Diagram

Use Case Diagrams In Figure 1 there are three actors, namely IT, runner and head of clinical information. where each actor must log in first before being able to access the outpatient medical record search software. After logging in, consumers can see a menu according to their individual needs, especially the statistical authority for outpatient medical record searches, then the authority for affected people's records and search reviews. outpatient medical records.

Figure 2 Login Activity Diagram

Activity Diagram login above explains the interaction between the admin or officer and the system, starting with entering the main web page of the internet site so that the gadget will display a login page and the admin enters a valid username and password, the device will display a

dashboard page, if the username or password entered is incorrect then the device will display an error message.

Figure 3 Activity Diagram Input patient data

Activity Diagrams The patient data input above explains the admin's interaction with the system starting with entering patient information according to the patient's social information. Once input, the machine will save the input information.

Figure 4 Activity Diagram Input search-borrow data

Activity Diagrams The loan search information input above explains the admin/clerk's interaction with the device which begins by inputting loan statistics, then the machine will validate the loan search statistics, if the information entered is not accurate then the machine will ask the runner to input valid records. If the facts entered are valid, the system will save the loan search data.

Figure 5 Search-Return Activity Diagram

Activity Diagrams Search-Return above states that the admin/runner relationship with the system begins with the officer accessing the search page, then the system displays the search page, the officer inputs data in the form of the medical record number, name and date of birth of the patient, then the admin clicks the search button, the system will display the data sought. . If the data you are looking for does not appear, the system will display a blank page, which means the database does not exist. If the data appears, the admin is asked to update the return data.

Figure 6 Activity Report Diagram

Activity Diagrams The report above states that the relationship between the admin/head of medical records and the system starts with the admin accessing the report page, then the system will display the report page, the admin inputs data in the form of borrowing and return dates, then the admin clicks the search button. If the search is successful the data will appear, if the search fails then

the system will display an empty report which means the database is empty, then the admin prints the report.

Figure 7 Sequence DiagramsLogin

Login Sequence Diagram The above mentions the process when the admin or officer logs in to the website, where the admin inputs the username and password, the system will process the login by verifying the username and password, the login is successful if the dashboard screen appears.

Figure 8 Sequence Diagram of Outpatient Medical Record Search

Sequence Diagrams The search above states that the process when officers search for medical records using a search application begins by filling in the patient's RM number, name and date of birth, the system will display proof of the search for data on borrowing and returning medical records, then the officer saves the data that has been used.

Figure 9 Logout Sequence Diagram

Sequence Diagrams The logout above explains the technicalities when an admin or officer logs out, where the officer accesses the website and the gadget displays the home screen, the officer logs out by clicking the logout button on the home dashboard, if the logout is successful then the device will display a login form.

After creating UML, the application design is carried out, following is the appearance of the application that has been created

1. Login Page

Figure 10 Login page

2. Search Application Dashboard

Figure 11 Search Application Dashboard

3. Medical Record Search data form

Figure 12 Medical Record Search data form

6. Medical Record Return Form

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the 'RUMAH SAKIT ISLAM IBNU SINA PADANG' medical record return form. The interface includes a sidebar with navigation options like 'ADMINISTRATOR', 'DATAMASTER', 'REKAM MEDIS', and 'LAPORAN'. The main form area contains fields for 'ID REGISTER', 'NOMOR REKAM MEDIS', 'NAMA PASIEN', 'RUANG PENYIMPANAN', 'NOMOR RAK', 'BARIS RAK', 'STATUS', 'TANGGAL PINJAM', 'NAMA PEMINJAM', 'KEPERLUAN', 'KETERANGAN', and 'TANGGAL KEMBALI'. The patient's name is 'NURMALA AGUSTINA' and the return date is '2023-07-03'. There are buttons for 'UPDATE', 'HAPUS', and 'KEMBALI' at the bottom of the form.

Figure 15 Medical Record Return Form

7. Report Sheet for Borrowing and Returning Medical Records

SISTEM Pencarian Berkas Rekam Medis
 Rumah Sakit Islam IBNU SINA PADANG
 Jl. Gajah Mada, Sn. Panglun Padang - Sumbar

LAPORAN Pencarian (Peminjaman / Pengembalian) Berkas Rekam Medis
 PERIODE : Tanggal 01 Juli 2023 s.d. 25 Juli 2023

NO. URUT	ID REGISTER	NOMOR RH	NAMA PASIEN	TGL. LAHIR	STATUS	TANGGAL PINJAM	TANGGAL KEMBALI	NAMA PEMINJAM	KEPERLUAN	KETERANGAN	RUANGAN	NOMOR RAK	BARIS RAK
1	23070346030	202307001	RAHMDA	22-12-1955	DIPINJAM	2023-07-25 03:46:00		JOKO	RAMAT INAP	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	13	4
2	2307122029	202307019	RAYLA HARFIDHA	24-05-2019	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-11 17:21:00	JOKO	IGD	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN B	3	4
3	2307122029	202307021	HERAKATI BINTI TALMAN	05-07-1974	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-11 17:21:00	MUL	RAMAT JALAN	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN C	1	2
4	2307119027	202307017	HUANDI BIN SALKHA	27-05-1973	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-11 17:22:00	JOKO	RAMAT JALAN	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN B	1	2
5	2307119026	202307015	SHAD HALLIKI	14-08-1975	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-11 17:22:00	MUL	RAMAT INAP	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	13	4
6	2307117025	202307013	SONI PUTRA	07-09-1982	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-10 17:22:00	JOKO	RAMAT INAP	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	13	4
7	2307117024	202307029	HULIKFILI BIN GAIK	02-02-1984	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-10 17:23:00	JOKO	IGD	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	15	4
8	2307116023	202307026	HOPELTI FAISAL	12-11-1983	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-11 17:23:00	PONG	PENGADILAN	YISIM	RUANGAN A	15	3
9	2307114022	202307012	SAYINA NAYITA	03-02-2010	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-11 17:23:00	MUL	IGD	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	4	4
10	2307114021	202307014	LIBERTY	20-12-1952	TERSEDIA	2023-07-10 17:21:00	2023-07-11 17:23:00	MUL	RAMAT INAP	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN A	13	3
11	2307113000	202307022	LISMANI	04-11-1981	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:22:00		JOKO	RAMAT INAP	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN C	1	2
12	2307111019	202307025	SALSA HURJANI	01-05-2001	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:21:00		JOKO	IGD	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	15	3
13	2307111018	202307024	BARTINA	11-02-1972	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:21:00		ADK	RAMAT JALAN	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN A	15	4
14	2307110017	202307030	LATU	04-05-1969	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:21:00		JOKO	RAMAT JALAN	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN B	14	1
15	2307109016	202307009	PASHON BUTAROTAR	08-07-1966	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:21:00		SUCI	ASURANSI	PEMINJAMAN REKAM MEDIS	RUANGAN A	14	3
16	2307109015	202307011	SONI PADANG	03-08-2005	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:08:00		SIDI	RAMAT JALAN	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN B	11	5
17	2307108014	202307008	MELIA FITRIA	27-04-1999	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:21:00		JOKO	ASURANSI	PEMINJAMAN REKAM MEDIS	RUANGAN A	14	3
18	2307107013	202307006	NOPRIANTI BINTI SAMDI	23-10-1983	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:21:00		DENI	RAMAT JALAN	PENCARIAN	RUANGAN A	14	5
19	2307107012	202307007	IGIT HASTUTIK	23-06-1974	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:07:00		HENDRI	RAMAT JALAN	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	14	5
20	2307106011	202307028	ALYANDA	20-10-1970	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:26:00		JOKO	PENGADILAN	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN A	15	4
21	2307105010	202307010	YERI ADRIAN DAFRI	05-05-1983	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:26:00		JOKO	RAMAT JALAN	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN A	14	3
22	2307105009	202307005	MIRWAN	23-09-1959	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:05:00		JOKO	RAMAT JALAN	PENCARIAN	RUANGAN A	14	5
23	2307104008	202307003	RUMAHAD AFDI NOPRIANUSAN	28-11-2003	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:08:00		MUL	IGD	PEMINJAMAN	RUANGAN A	14	4
24	2307105008	202307004	NURMALA AGUSTINA	27-08-1983	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:08:00		MUL	ASURANSI	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	4	14
25	2307104006	202307002	HRIADI BIN YASIA	25-06-1988	DIPINJAM	2023-07-10 17:03:00		JOKO	RAMAT INAP	MELIHAT RIWAYAT PENYAKIT	RUANGAN A	14	4

Figure 16 Report on Borrowing and Returning Medical Records

Then it can be tested on the system using Black Box testing which can be seen in the following table:

Table 1 Black Box Testing on the system

No	Scenario	System Reaction	Results
1.	Login Enter the user ID Username and Password	1. See whether the data entered is valid or not by checking user data. 2. Enter the Outpatient Medical Record Borrowing and Returning Data Search application	√
2.	Input Patient Data -Enter patient data according to the existing columns -Display data saved successfully	Tests whether the information entered is valid or not, saves data to the database.	√
3.	Loan data input -Enter loan data according to the existing columns -Displays data saved successfully	Test whether the information entered is valid or not save mortgage facts to database	√
4.	Return data input -Enter return data according to the existing columns -Displays data saved successfully	Check whether the entered data is valid or not Save return data to database	
5.	Searching for Data -Enter keywords in the form of the patient's medical record number, patient's name and patient's date of birth -Clicking on the search data you want to search for	Select the data to search Displays the searched search data Save search data from database	√*
6.	Report -Select the report menu in the application	Displays the report menu	√

	-Enter keywords in the form of the start date and end date of the report. Search for data on borrowing and returning outpatient medical records. -Select the print report menu	Displays report data according to the keywords entered Print Report	
7.	Logout Select the logout menu	Logout	

From the table above, it can be seen that the results of each examination starting from the login process, how to enter statistics and update statistics as well as displaying outpatient medical record search reports have gone quite well and are in accordance with the desired wishes.

CONCLUSION

1. The process of identifying the input and output component system process flow obtained process searches conducted electronically can saving time And improve service processes.
2. The design of the medical record search application has gone well And fluent, because with the information system you can search for outpatient medical records makes it easier for officers to carry out the search process medical records, so officers no longer need to look for medical records in various storage places and save search time.
3. Component testing and effectiveness obtained by component displays and menus there are appropriate, easy to understand and more outpatient medical record searches faster compared to the manual method because of the components in the application is appropriate because each of these components has been proven capable makes the officer's job easier.

REFERENCES

- Iqromi Nugra, H. (2020). Design and Development of a Web-Based Village Information System Assisted by the Panca Budi Development University. *Pancabudi Journal*, 14.
- RI Minister of Health Regulation No. 24, 151 JDIH BPK RI 10 (2022).
- Mirna Septria, R., Lestari, T., Mulyono, S., Apikes, M., Husada Karanganyar, M., Apikes, D., & Karanganyar, MH (2011). Review of the Implementation of the Medical Record Document Alignment System in the Filling Room at Dr. Regional General Hospital. *R. Soedjati Soemodiharjo Grobogan Regency* (Issue 2).
- RI Minister of Health Regulation Number. 3 of 2020, 39 Implementation Science 1 (2020). <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Details/152506/permenkes-no-3-tahun-2020>

Copyright © The Author(s)

Miracle Get Journal Vol. 01 , No. 2 , May (2024) 1-14

Ritonga, ZA, Faradila, ; 2, & Sari, M. (2019). Review of the Medical Record File Storage System at H Adam Malik Central General Hospital in 2019.

Hospital H Abdul Aziz Marabahan. (2019). Guidelines for Organizing Medical Records. 1–48. <https://repository.stikeshb.ac.id/9/>

Yurindra. (2017). Engineering Software (pe mold). Online Public Access Catalog. <https://opac.perpusnas.go.id/DetailOpac.aspx?id=1143824#>

Zulfallah, FH, & Hidayatuloh, S. (2021). Analysis and Design of an Internship Registration Information System at the Inspectorate General of the Ministry of Education and Culture. Infocom Essentials Journal: Journal of Information Systems and Computer Systems Essentials, 5(1), 26–34. <https://doi.org/10.55886/infokom.v5i1.294>